

What Drives the Intention of Students to Make Public Complaints?

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Abstract: *The importance of studying how dissatisfied customers complain has become increasingly important, not only for businesses but also for Higher Education Institutions. This article explores the factors influencing students' intention to make public complaints about service failures at Vietnamese higher education. Qualitative research, including In-depth Interviews, Social Media, and Critical Incident Techniques, were conducted to collect data related to the complaint behavior of students and analyze the main factor affecting students' intention to make complaints in this research. After that, 213 surveys were sent to students in six economic universities in Hanoi, Vietnam. Data from 194 usable survey were analyzed by SPSS software and a series of statistical techniques to identify factors affecting students' intention to make complaints in tertiary schools. The research results show that four variables, including self-confidence, perceived difficulty of complaint, perceived likelihood of successful complaint, and the provider's responsiveness, significantly affect students' intention to make public complaints. Additionally, students' self-confidence has the strongest positive impact on the intention of students to make public complaints. The findings of this study could assist school managers to early detect service failure and improve the complaint process used by Higher Education Institutions to address student dissatisfaction because of their negative impact on service quality and the university's reputation.*

Keywords: Complaint Behavior, Higher Education, Public Complaint, Service Failure, Student Complaint Intention

I. INTRODUCTION

On a daily basis, millions of customers worldwide experience dissatisfied products or services (Reichheld, 1996). Some of them complain directly to the firm or service staff, but others just keep silent about unpleasant experiences and never trust the business again (Singh, 1988; Voorhees, Brady, and Horowitz, 2006). However, most researchers reveal that the majority of dissatisfied customers do not voice (Day et al., 1981; Stephens and Gwinner, 1998) that makes the firm never have the opportunity to solve the problem and retain the customer loyalty (Jin, 2010). Thus, it is important for management to be aware of the factors that cause dissatisfied customers' intention to voice their complaints - that is, the tendency to complain directly to service providers or other third parties, which gives the companies opportunities to correct their mistakes effectively and reduce the harmful effects.

A huge number of research have been conducted to determine the factors that influence customers' intention to complain. The majority of them has been focused on the sectors that have low exit barriers or exchanging costs for customers, such as retail stores (Andreassen, 2000; Blodgett, Wakefield, & Barnes, 1995; Kim et al., 2003; Strauss & Hill, 2001), hospitality industries (Singh & Wilkes, 1996; Voorhees & Brady, 2005) or restaurant (Heung & Lam, 2003; Cheng & Lam, 2008; Mattila & Ro, 2008). However, far less attention has been paid on complaint management in the higher education sector, especially in Vietnam and Southeast Asia.

In Vietnam, the recent proliferation of private universities or international institutions with attractive curriculums and competitive tuition fees offers students having numerous choices. This situation put public universities under pressure of improving service quality to increase student satisfaction. Therefore, exploring factors affecting students' intention to make complaints in higher education will provide important evidence to education organizations to understand their complaint behavior and develop appropriate service recovery strategies, followed by enhancing service quality.

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This paper investigates determinants affecting Vietnamese students' intention to make a public complaint about service failures in higher education. The paper begins with literature reviews on service failure at higher education and customers' intention to make complaints of service failures. In order to get insight into a specific higher education service, six economic universities in Hanoi, Vietnam were chosen to collect data. In this research, three different kinds of quantitative methods, including Social media, Critical incident technique, and in-depth interviews, were conducted to collect data related to complaint behavior of students and analyze the main factor affecting students' intention to make complaints in this research. After that, a survey questionnaire is applied to discover factors affecting students' intention to make public complaints in higher education. Finally, the paper concludes with some implications to effectively manage the complaint behavior of students.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Service Failure at Higher Education

The service failure in the study is defined from the perspective of the gap between perception and expectation, whereby, in the minds of customers, there are always certain expectations when they buy a product or use a service, and when expectations do not match perceptions, the service will fail (Shapiro et al., 2006). According to the research results of Mohr and Bitner (1995) and Chuang et al. (2012), service failure has two sides, related to process and results; in other words, service failure will occur when consumers are not satisfied with the service delivery process, or when the performance/quality of the product is lower than their expectations (Lewis and Spyropoulos, 2001 and Gye-Soo, 2007).

Currently, in the market mechanism, higher education is generally considered a type of service and higher education institutions served as a service provider. So, failure to provide quality services will lead to service failures in higher education institutions and create negative student reactions such as negative word of mouth, exert negative impacts on universities' images, etc. (Hlophe, 2016). Therefore, under increasingly fierce competitive pressure, understanding the cause of service failures to handle customer complaints and complaints is an indispensable part of the error handling process for service restoration.

Categorizing the causes of failure helps to identify common types of service failure incidents and provides information for a more thorough analysis of why these types of service failures occur. In other words, it provides additional information to reduce similar incidents in the future (Gonzalez, Hoffman, and Ingram, 2005).

Specifically, in higher education institutions, service incidents can involve teaching, testing, libraries, laboratories, administration, infrastructure, and others, such as private and dormitory facilities. Based on studies such as Swanson and Davis (2000), Voss (2009), and Voss et al. (2010), service failures in the education sector can be classified into three groups.

- Group I service failures relate to professors' reactions to service delivery system failures, including failures in core services in higher education, such as late arrival of faculty and failure to deliver study materials. For students, teaching is difficult to understand, etc.
- Group II service failures concern the faculty's response to the needs and requirements of the students, for example, asking for more teaching, changing class time because of the same subject, etc.
- Group III service failures are related to unsolicited actions such as rude behavior, impoliteness, screaming, etc.

2.2. Student Complaint Intention

Most customer complaint behavior research models presume that complaining is one of the most direct and meaningful ways for consumers to express their dissatisfaction with a product or service failure to the provider. However, complaining does not always stem from dissatisfaction, and dissatisfaction does not always lead to complaining behavior; therefore, dissatisfaction is not a sufficient condition for customers to complain (Day, 1984; Singh & Pandya, 1991).

The definition of customer complaint behavior (CCB) has attracted considerable attention and interest from consumer behavior researchers over the last few decades (Day & Landon, 1977; Jacoby & Jaccard, 1981; Singh, 1988). Singh's CCB definition is the most common definition: "CCB is a set of multiple (behavioral and non-behavioral) responses, some or all of which are triggered by perceived dissatisfaction with a purchase episode". (Singh, 1988)

In higher education, the concept of students' complaint behavior is often included in more comprehensive investigations of service quality (Owlia & Aspinwall, 1996; LeBlanc & Nguyen, 1997; Bennett & Kane, 2010). The Office for the Independent Adjudicator (2014) defined a student complaint as "an expression of dissatisfaction by one or more students about a provider's action or lack of action, or about the standard of service provided by or on behalf of the provider." Much like in any other sector, dissatisfied students have a variety of potential responses at their disposal, some of which are undetectable (Su, 1998) and all of which can prove potentially damaging to the university. However, unlike products,

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the student learning experience cannot be standardized, leading to inconsistency. When students are not aware of values or learning experiences not matching their expectations, they are more likely to intend to make public complaints (Arthur, 1994; Nyer & Gopinath, 2005). The intention of students to make complaints focuses on the failure to evaluate and classify the level and the student's frustration with the university's services.

The reported complaints from students of higher education institutions are mainly from issues related to faculty and the general learning environment (Arthur, 1994); Van Hoorebeek & Gale (2011) reports that a variety of factors causes disputes and complaints from students to administrators, but what is expected are issues related to finance and law/policy, which recommend that university management resolve them from the outset before they become crises.

This CCB classification model was compiled from previous research of Day and Landon (1977), Singh (1988), Singh (1990), Zeithaml, Bitner and Gremler (2017), and Wirtz and Lovelock (2016). Usually, dissatisfied consumers show 3 types of complaint behaviors, namely: public complaint action, private complaint action and take no complaint action. It is important that consumers can take any one action or combine two or more types of complaints. Research shows that unhappy individuals often use multiple methods of complaining simultaneously (Mousavi & Esfidani, 2013; Mukherjee et al., 2009; Singh & Pandya, 1991).

Human actions are controlled by intentions, but not all intentions carry out the relevant actions (Ajzen, 1985). Reviewing the current literature, most literature focuses on identifying determinants of consumer complaint behavior rather than complaining intention. Therefore, in this study, combining the framework of complaint behavior and intention, the authors focus on the concept of students' intention to make public complaints with Vietnamese higher education institutions.

Intentions are assumed to capture the motivational factors that influence behavior; they are indications of how hard people are willing to try and how much of an effort they are planning to exert to perform the behavior (Ajzen, 1985). Many studies have also confirmed intention as a motivational factor, which motivates an individual to be willing to take action.

When students do public complaint actions, they can choose to make a direct complaint to the university or to complain to a third party.

Complain directly to the university

A public complaint is generally taken to mean any visible action taken directly towards the institution responsible for the dissatisfaction. Unhappy students can also consider speaking directly to lecturers about their dissatisfaction. If the student finds the school can respond to its problems, they will be more likely to complain directly to their university. Dissatisfied students may consider speaking directly to faculty academic advisors or using a semester-end faculty assessment form of their dissatisfaction. Students decide to make complaints hoping that the problem can be recognized and fixed quickly. Moreover, they believe that their complaint action can help those with the same problem (Yoke, 2018). Another way students can express their grievances is by emailing the professor or using a social media-based feedback system managed by the university. Today's online social networking environment provides more opportunities for students to complain.

Complain to a Third Party

Students may want to take their complaints to a third party who may act as a mediator in the conflict process in more severe situations. This may include seeking advice from other separate agencies such as the Student Union, the Ministry of Education and Training, etc. Many universities have not exhaustively documented complaints at the informal level, making it more difficult to assess overall student dissatisfaction rates. East Asian students often have less common third-party responses than other forms (Hart & Coates, 2011).

III. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Many studies have been done to find out the factors that affect Customer Complaint Intention (CCI). The results reveal that there are five groups of factors that have relationships with CCI:

1. Individual (Demographical, Psychological, Personality, Emotional, Experience...)
2. Sociocultural
3. Situation (Economic, Perceived, Seriousness)
4. Service provider (Perceived importance of product/service, Store reputation, Provider's responsiveness, Likelihood of success,...)
5. Market (Degree of market competition, Industry structure)

Although many studies have been conducted to understand CCI, few studies of CCI have been tested in the educational environment, especially in Vietnam's education. In this research, there are eight factors considered that may have relationships with CCI: academic level, gender, self-confidence, customer loyalty, attitude towards complaint behavior, perceived likelihood of successful complaint, perceived difficulty of complaint and provider's responsiveness.

Demographic characteristics

Academic level: Heung (2000) suggests that younger consumers are more likely to choose to complain to the provider when dissatisfied. Warland et al. (1975), Day and Landon (1977) state that people who publicly complain are younger. Some of the students who have stayed for three or four years at the university have developed a personal relationship with members of staff working in different departments. They are likely to be more tolerant of service failures than first-year students who have just joined the university (Msosa, 2019). Based on these findings, the following hypothesis is:

H1: The younger the students are, the higher the intention to make public complaints.

Gender is considered as a factor influencing CCI because previous studies show varying results. Phau and Baird (2008) state that there is no clear difference between male and female in complaint. According to Keng et al. (1995), female consumers are often more willing to complain than men and tell others if they are satisfied with the provider's complaint recovery (Lewis, 1983). On the other hand, Manickas and Shea (1997) find that male consumers are likely to complain directly. Because of the difference in nature, women are often more emotional than men, which may affect the choice of complaining behavior of the two genders. Therefore, women can trendy to complain more than men, and our following hypothesis is:

H2: Female students are more likely to complain than male students.

Self-Confidence

Many studies have found that confidence is an aspect of personal characteristics. Bearden and Teel (1980) reveal that confidence can predict intention to complain. If consumers are more confident, they are likely to voice their dissatisfaction because they tend to be confident in their decisions and assertive in presenting their opinions and ideas (Chelminski, 2007). On the other hand, consumers who lack confidence in their abilities may feel resigned, fearful, and assume that events around them are out of their control. For these customers, in experiencing dissatisfaction, they might choose not to complain because they believe that there is no point in complaining (Bearden and Teel, 1980). This argument suggests that there is a positive relationship between self-confidence and CCI and it leads us to H3 which hypothesis can be:

H3: The more confident students are, the higher the intention to make public complaints.

Customer Loyalty

According to Durukan, Gokdenizm & Bozaci (2012), the concept of loyalty is expressed through words such as dedication, commitment, dependability, perseverance, patience, etc. Fornell and Wernerfelt (1988) show that loyal customers will tend to complain more often than disloyal customers in the case of dissatisfaction. Blodgett and Granbois (1992) study Hirschman's (1970) model and reveal that loyal customers are more likely to seek help or compensation from the supplier less likely to spread negative word of mouth if they are not satisfied. Similarly, loyal customers are less likely to complain to a third party (Oh, 2003). Evanschitzky, Brock and Blut (2011) also performed a study to know the impact of loyalty on the intention to complain and the results show that the more loyal to the supplier, the more willing the customer is to show the intention to complain. Therefore, the following hypothesis is:

H4: The more loyal students are, the higher the intention to make public complaints about service failure in higher education.

Attitude towards complaint behavior

The attitudes toward a specific behavior would influence the intention to respond and decide whether or not to act. Similarly, a customer's attitudes toward complaint making itself will affect the tendency to complain (Jin, 2010). Some people believe that complaining is justified and tend to hold a more positive attitude towards receiving compensation through complaining. Research by LiYin Jin (2010) has shown that if customers have positive attitudes towards performing complaining behavior by optimistically thinking that they will get compensation from the provider, the propensity of the customers to conduct a direct complaint will increase. On the other hand, some customers think negatively, and they are less likely to complain directly to the provider and more likely to engage in negative behaviors such as switching to other competitors or using negative word of mouth about the provider's services (Blodgett and Granbois, 1992). Based on the above arguments, the following hypothesis is:

H5: The more positive the student's attitude towards complaint, the more intention to make public complaint behavior.

Perceived likelihood of successful complaint

Previous studies have shown that the greater the likelihood of complaints, the more likely customers will complain directly to the provider (Singh, 1989; Richins, 1987). Ajzen (1985) suggests that successful prediction will be based on customer resources and perceived opportunities. Before making a purchase, customers can find information about the service. When a failure occurs, they will gain more confidence from having enough information or resources to object to the supplier or third party. (Busseri, Lefcourt, & Kerton, 1998). This leads us to H6 and it can be:

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H6: The greater the perceived possibility of successful complaint, the stronger the intention is for the student to make a direct complaint.

Perceived difficulty of complaint

Day (1984) has developed a model that shows that the customer will firstly consider the costs and benefits of complaining, perform an analysis, then decide whether to complain or not. Andreasen (1988) also suggests that one of the three reasons why unsatisfied customers do not intend to complain is that after the cost and benefit analysis process of the complaint, they perceive the benefit to be less than the cost or the cost to be higher than the benefit obtained after making the complaint. These are purely customers' subjective assessments of the difference between the benefits gained through direct complaints and the costs incurred, so there is a direct impact on the customer's complaint intention. Therefore, there is a positive relationship between the perceived difficulty of complaint and CCI, so our following hypothesis is:

H7: The more students are aware of the disadvantages of publicly complaining, the lower the tendency to make direct complaints.

Provider's responsiveness

The provider's responsiveness to customer complaints about service failure is another factor that needs to be considered since the supplier's attitude and response will directly affect the service provider's response to complaints intentions, complaining behavior of customers. When a service provider is assessed to be unresponsive or has a superficial attitude in receiving complaints, customers are less likely to complain to the provider (Richins, 1983) and more likely to choose negative behaviors to express their dissatisfaction, such as using negative word-of-mouth or not complaining but silently changing service providers. Hence, the following hypothesis is:

H8: The higher the university's responsiveness, the higher the tendency for students to make direct complaints.

Figure 1. Hypothesize Conceptual Model

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Instrument Research

The authors combined three qualitative research methods including Social Media, In-Depth Interviews, and Critical Incident Technique. Specifically through the method of using social media to find information and subjects for the in-depth interview process. A combination of in-depth interviews and critical incident research to ask informants to recall a specific event and explain the circumstances surrounding the incident - to collect information about the service failure complaint process of the interviewees. There is also a basis for evaluating the questionnaire, checking the appropriateness of each factor and observations used in the study, thereby identifying the factors that profoundly affect the intention to complain of students at universities in Hanoi.

In addition, to determine the effectiveness of the survey questionnaire, the team chose to conduct pilot test research with 40 survey samples to re-evaluate and adjust the questionnaire before conducting the official survey.

Collected data is processed and analyzed by techniques of SPSS 22.0 and ASMOS 22.0 software through steps of Reliability Testing (Cronbach's Alpha); exploratory factor analysis (EFA); Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), and Hypothesis Testing by Multiple Linear Regression. The T-test and multiple regression analysis were used to analyze the relationship.

Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire is divided into four parts. *The opening part* introduces the information, purpose, and meaning of the study to the survey participants and, at the same time, ensures the confidentiality of the survey participants. *Part*

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1: Find out personal information, frequency of complaint, and channels to make public complaint behavior of survey participants. *Part 2:*Analyze service failure situations that trigger/lead to public complaints. *Part 3:* Find out the level of agreement of survey participants with personality characteristics, factors of loyalty, attitude, etc., which are believed to influence the students' public complaint intention for service failures at higher education. The questionnaire mainly uses a 5-point Likert Scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) for each measurement variable.

Sample/Data Collection

The data for the study was collected through a survey by a questionnaire sent to students of many different universities in Hanoi city. Data were collected during the study period from October 2021 to February 2022. Due to the epidemic's impact, the questionnaires were sent (distributed) online through social networking sites (Facebook, Zalo, Instagram, etc.). The total number of survey samples is 213. Among the returned questionnaires, 19 were rendered unusable due to inconsistent or incomplete answers, thus leaving us with a final sample size of 194.

Variables measurement

Measurement scales are adapted based on previously published studies to examine various items of the model. Mainly adjusted, sorted, and selected based on the scale of Phau and Baird (2008), Singh (1990), Kim et al. (2003), and previous research papers on the same topic to suit the context of Vietnamese higher education.

Table 1. Measurement scales of the study

Variables	Items	References
Gender		Phau and Baird (2008); Metehan and Zengin, (2011).
Age		Singh (1990); Phau and Baird (2008)
Self-Confidence (SC)	1. I believe in my communication ability. 2. I don't hesitate to ask a question to my lecturer. 3. Speaking up in front of an audience is not a problem for me.	Chelminiski and Coulter (2007)
Customer Loyalty (CL)	1. I often say positive things about my university to others. 2. I recommend my university to someone confused between many options. 3. I consider my university my first priority in the future. 4. I won't complain publicly if my complaint behavior adversely affects my universities' reputation.	Ashraf (2013)
Attitude towards complaint behavior (ACB)	1. Complaining about unsatisfactory service is students' right. 2. I don't hesitate to complain about service failure. 3. I feel comfortable when complaining directly to the university about service failure. 4. I feel obliged to complain directly about dissatisfied service to my university.	Blodgett (1994); Singh and Wilkes (1996); Kim et al., (2003); Azam et al., (2013)
Perceived likelihood of successful complaint (PLS)	1. If I complain about my dissatisfaction with the university, they will take appropriate action. 2. If I complain about my dissatisfaction with the university, my problem will be resolved effectively. 3. I think I have the capability (knowledge, experience, skills...) to make a successful complaint. 4. I believe the university will speedily handle the complaints to preserve the universities' reputation.	Oh (2003); Rizwan et al., (2013)

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<p>Perceived difficulty of complaint (PDC)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I am afraid lecturers/ university staff will not support me to resolve complaints about service failure. 2. Making public complaints takes a lot of time and effort. 3. I find it is difficult to implement the complaint procedures. 4. I am worried about receiving objections when I make public complaints (especially via social media). 	<p>Richins (1980); Singh (1989, 1990); Oh (2003)</p>
<p>Provider's responsiveness (PR)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The lecturers/ members of the university staff usually support me to solve my problem. 2. My university receives and solves my problem quickly 3. It is easy and convenient to register complaints at my university 4. My university encourages students to complain when they face problems. 5. My university has publicized places to register complaints. 6. My university has different platforms or communication channels for registering complaints. 	<p>Lala (2011); Msosa (2019)</p>
<p>Public complaint Intention (IN)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I would complain publicly to my university about service failure that makes me dissatisfied. 2. I would offer my university to take proper actions to resolve the problem that I am facing. 3. I would inform my university so that they can provide better service in the future. 	<p>Kim et al., (2003); Kim and Boo (2011)</p>

V. RESULTS

General Information

In this study, out of 213 questionnaires, a valid sample of 194 was used for the final analysis. Among 194 students who participated in the study, females comprised 59,8%, while respondents of the opposite gender accounted for 40,2%. In sample universities, the majority of respondents come from 3 popular universities which have larger student populations: National Economics University (29,9%), Thuong Mai University (19,1%), and Vietnam National University (18%). Third-year students contributed 47,2% to the sample, while second-year students contributed 24,2%, the remaining respondents were studying first and fourth year (28,4%).

In 194 sample respondents collected, nearly 62% of respondents have made public complaint behavior and 17% of them have frequently complained publicly at universities. Among 120 students who have made public complaints, complaining directly to lecturers or university administrators is the most common channel with 73 people ever used, followed by complaining through Facebook groups (52 users), and responses to third parties represented the smallest segment. Furthermore, students regularly complain about service failure related to Academic dimensions such as lecture quality, course content, fairness of grading, and accessibility of faculty (30,8%) or incidents referred to information technology system (such as updating tuition information inaccurately/slowly, errors of the credit registration system or being entered incorrect personal information) which also account nearly the same proportion (30%).

Reliability analysis

The results for scale consistency using coefficient Cronbach's Alpha confirm that the measures of the major structure present good reliability with all coefficients of Alpha reported surpass Nunally's (1978) criteria (> 0.60) for reliability acceptability. However, the item CL4 has Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted indicator higher than Cronbach's Alpha of total CL scale ($0.842 > 0.812$) so that it had been deleted to advanced scale reliability.

After deleted invalid items, all of the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients are at acceptable range: SC (0.879), CL (0.842), ACB (0.763), PLS (0.803), PDC (0.796), PR (0.875) and IN (0.840).

Analysis of EFA's Factor results

After reliability examination, EFA factor analysis was conducted based on an exploiting method with principal Components analysis and Varimax rotation. The analysis results obtained item PLS1 having a difference between load factors less than 0.2 that does not match the convergent condition. After removing this invalid item, the next results of EFA analysis of 23 remaining variables showed that the KMO coefficient is $0.839 > 0.5$, $\text{sig} = 0.000 < 0.05$ and other

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values meet the statistical requirements. Finally, six factors were totally extracted and satisfactory to continue the next analysis steps. The EFA analysis result was shown in the table 2.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) results

Model Fit Evaluation

CFA which is a multivariate statistical procedure was conducted to verify the suitability of the measurement scales. The general accepted standards for model fit are: Chi-square/df ≤ 3 , goodness of fit index (GFI > 0.80), comparative fit index (CFI > 0.90), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI ≥ 0.9) and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA $\leq 0,06$). Table 3 shows the results of CFA with model fit indicators are good enough for further analysis.

Table 2. Analysis Pattern Matrix

	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
PR2	.786					
PR3	.770					
PR6	.726					
PR5	.723					
PR1	.709					
PR4	.621					
SC2		.882				
SC1		.833				
SC3		.830				
PDC2			.816			
PDC3			.811			
PDC1			.771			
PDC4			.736			
CL3				.802		
CL2				.773		
CL1				.745		
ACB2					.798	
ACB1					.744	
ACB4					.671	
ACB3					.604	
PLS2						.744
PLS3						.741

PLS4						.717
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Table 3. Index of the fit of the model

Index of fit	Chi-square/df	GFI	CFI	TLI	RMSEA	PCLOSE
Value	1.575	0.869	0.937	0.926	0.055	0.241

Composite Reliability and Convergent Validity

The scale is considered reliable when the Composite Reliability (CR) is greater than 0.7 and the Average Extracted Variance (AVE) is above 0.5 (Hair et al., 2010). In addition, convergent validity was assessed by factor loading > 0.5 and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) above 0.5 is acceptable (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2010).

In this study, after conducting the first analysis, the AVE of two factors was lower than 0.5 (includes F_ACB is 0.454 and F_PDC is 0.498). After deleting 2 items (ACB1 and PDC4) due to the lowest factor loadings of the scales, all the analysis indicators were at the acceptable level (Table 4).

Table 4. Factor loading, Composite Reliability and Convergent Validity

Scales	Items	Factor Loading	CR	AVE
PR	PR2	.764	0.876	0.541
	PR3	.752		
	PR6	.721		
	PR1	.665		
	PR5	.769		
	PR4	.738		
SC	SC2	.917	0.883	0.717
	SC3	.833		
	SC1	.785		
PDC	PDC2	.836	0.785	0.552
	PDC3	.633		
	PDC1	.745		
CL	CL3	.820	0.843	0.641
	CL2	.803		
	CL1	.779		
ACB	ACB2	.689	0.754	0.506
	ACB4	.707		
	ACB3	.737		

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PLS	PLS2	.820	0.778	0.541
	PLS3	.678		
	PLS4	.701		

Regression Results

The multiple regression analyses were used to examine the relationship of these factors to the dependent variable “public complaint intention”. The analysis results showed that the Sig value of the F statistical test is 0.000 (< 0.05), which indicates the regression model is suitable. The Adjusted R2 value (0.445) indicates that 44,5% of the variance in student’s intention to complain is accounted for by the variables of our proposed model.

Among six factors, four factors (Self-Confidence, Perceived likelihood of successful complaint, Perceived difficulty of complaint, and Provider’s responsiveness) had acceptable statistical significance (p values less than 0.05). Out of these appropriate factors, Self-Confidence was the most significant variable in explaining students’ intention to complain ($\beta = 0.293$, $p = 0.000$), followed by Perceived difficulty of complaint ($\beta = 0.204$, $p = 0.000$), Perceived likelihood of successful complaint ($\beta = 0.202$, $p = 0.003$) and Provider’s responsiveness ($\beta = 0.166$, $p = 0.026$). While SC, PLS and PR factors show the significant positive relationship to the dependent variable, regression results confirm a considerable negative relationship between PDC and complaint intention. Also, the tolerance of each variable (VIF) was below 2, which means there is no critical multicollinearity problem.

Table 5. Results of Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.	VIF
	B	Std.Error	Beta			
(Hàng số)	.884	.343		2.578	.011	
SC	.296	.063	.293	4.722	.000	1.343
CL	.108	.065	.111	1.650	.101	1.573
ACB	.143	.075	.120	1.898	.059	1.398
PLS	.219	.073	.202	3.008	.003	1.575
PDC	-.197	.053	-.204	-3.732	.000	1.037
PR	.194	.086	.166	2.241	.026	1.901

Note. R2 = 0.463; Adjusted R2 = 0.445
Durbin-Waston = 1.781

Furthermore, a t-test analysis was conducted to find the differences between demographic variables as well. The result reveals that there is no significant difference between the two genders of the sample (Sig. = 0.092 > 0.05). However, the second-year-student group displayed a higher intention to make a public complaint than the first-year-student group (Sig. = 0.039 < 0.05), and no considerable difference was shown between the remaining level of academics. The hypothesis testing results were exhibited in the below table:

Table 6. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Content	Results
H1	<i>The younger the students are, the higher the intention to make public complaints.</i>	Reject
H2	<i>Female students are more likely to complain than male students.</i>	Reject
H3	<i>The more confident students are, the higher the intention to make public complaints.</i>	Accept

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H4	<i>The more loyal students are, the higher the intention to make public complaints</i>	Reject
H5	<i>The more positive the student's attitude towards complaint, the more intention to make public complaint behavior.</i>	Reject
H6	<i>The greater the perceived possibility of successful complaint, the stronger the intention is for the student to make a direct complaint.</i>	Accept
H7	<i>The more students are aware of the disadvantages of publicly complaining, the lower the tendency to make direct complaints.</i>	Accept
H8	<i>The higher the university's responsiveness, the higher the tendency for students to make direct complaints.</i>	Accept

VI. DISCUSSION

The authors identified this study as the first official study in Vietnam and one of a few studies in the world about factors influencing students' intention to make public complaints about service failure in the context of higher education.

Student complaint behavior

According to the statistics in this study, of the 194 respondents sampled, nearly 62% are publicly complaining, and 17% are often publicly complaining to the university. Many studies reveal that only 5% to 10% of unsatisfied consumers really complain to the supplier after a service failure (Tax and Brown, 1998; Ennew and Schoefer, 2003). Nevertheless, due to the low alternative services ability in higher education, students hardly leave the institution after a failure. Thus, students will complain more to the university to reclaim their rights. On the other hand, the findings of a study by Ngai et al. (2007), Asian customers with high power distance, collectivism, and uncertainty avoidance, often complain less than European customers for fear of "losing face" while complaining and being unfamiliar or even unaware of the complaint channels. This conclusion is reasonable in the context of higher education in Vietnam, where there is a wide gap between students and lecturers. Unlike students in developed countries, most Vietnamese students still feel unconfident and uncomfortable when speaking with professors or university administrative departments. Therefore, Vietnamese students are less likely to complain than students from developed countries.

Demographics

The demographics, including gender, academic level, examined in this study did not exert any effect on students' intention to make public complaints to the school. These findings are similar to the results of prior research by Su and Bao (2001), Sujithamrak and Lam (2005), Phau and Baird (2008), and Lala and Priluck (2011).

Student's complaint behavior to service failure

When a service failure occurs, the most preferred option of students is to complain directly to faculty/academic advisors/school administrators via in-person communication or texting via email, phone, social media channels, etc. However, complaining to a third party is less common, perhaps due to a lack of awareness of the instructional information. Thanks to advanced information technology, universities allow students to easily access and make more public complaints, such as through student support Facebook groups or the university's official homepage. So it is perhaps not surprising that complaining directly through social media is the most preferred form of reaction. This situation may be appropriate for Asian students, particularly Vietnamese students, who are hesitant to complain to faculty or staff directly (face-to-face) (Yau, 1988).

Self-Confidence

This study result indicates that self-confidence strongly influences the intention of students to make public complaints. These findings align with Bearden and Teel's (1980), and Chelminski and Coulter's (2007) study, which examined the influence of individualism and self-confidence on customers' complaint intentions. In general, the higher the amount of self-confidence, the more likely the individual will be to exert more effort in expressing dissatisfaction. In contrast, less confident students are less likely to express their frustration about service failures and to contribute to the university's suggestions for improving the service quality.

Loyalty

The results of the quantitative analysis show that university loyalty has no relationship with students' public complaints intention. This result is similar to Oh (2003) study, which found that loyalty did not affect customer complaint behavior. Nevertheless, many authors such as Cheng and Lam (2008), and Rizwan et al. (2013) pointed out that customer loyalty has an effect on their ability to complain and even directly affects customer complaint behavior

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(Hirschman, 1970; Ashraf et al., 2013). This situation could be explained by the fact that students rarely choose to drop out of college and transfer to another. Additionally, university conversion is not an easy choice for a student due to many barriers such as cost, time, effort, etc.

Attitude toward complaint behavior

This study's quantitative analysis results indicate that attitudes toward complaining do not affect students' public complaint intention. These results differ from previous studies of Blodgett and Granbois (1992), Oh (2003), Erdogan and Norman (2011), they have suggested that a customer's attitude towards complaining strongly influences customers' complaint behavior. But this is a reasonable outcome in higher education because approximately 40% of the survey participants have never made public complaints before. However, this finding is similar to the study of Lala and Priluck (2011), which found that attitude toward complaining did not make students any more likely to complain to the college, but the attitude toward complaining was associated with intention to complain to others using the web. Students with a more positive attitude toward complaining are likely to broadcast their experience on the web through posts on blogs, social media, and e-mail blasts. This is particularly troubling since such students will tell the world about the episode but not give the school a chance to make it right.

Perceived likelihood of successful complaint

The "Perceived likelihood of successful complaint" was identified as one of the critical factors driving students to public complaint intention. This finding is similar to previous studies of Singh (1989), Kim et al. (2003); Jin (2010); and Rizwan et al. (2013), they have documented that the likelihood of successful complaining positively influences customer complaint intention. Although switching to another institution when service failure in higher education occurs is difficult, the perceived low likelihood of successful complaints can lead students to spread negative word-of-mouth to their friends, family, and others. Consequently, the university misses out on valuable feedback that could help them improve their service quality.

Perceived difficulty of complaint

"Perceived difficulty of complaining" is the second important factor (after Self-Confidence) that negatively affects intention to make public complaints with a standardized regression coefficient (-0.206) and Sig. (0.000). This finding is consistent with the study results by Jin (2010) and Azam et al. (2013). In other words, perceived difficulty of complaint is also an important factor preventing students' public complaint intention. Because the complaint procedure in Vietnamese universities is delayed, with many cumbersome and complex documentation, students feel difficult and time-consuming to find and carry out the complaints process.

Provider's responsiveness

The study's findings agree with those of the previous research by Mattila and Wirtz (2004), and Blodgett and Anderson's (2000) that the "Provider Responsiveness" (The higher education institutions) positively affected students' public complaint intention. Students intend to make public complaints when the university offers a diverse, convenient complaints platform and the speed to handle and solve problems quickly. So, this is also an essential factor contributing to helping universities recognize and improve the complaints system.

VII. IMPLICATIONS FOR FACULTY AND SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS

Faculty and School Administrators should develop a more effective complaint system for increasing student satisfaction by early detecting service failures and improving service quality. The following recommendations emanate from the findings of this study.

First and foremost, universities should raise students' awareness of the importance of making public complaints by demonstrating that doing so not only helps solve their problems but also helps institutions improve service quality to bring more benefits to students. Universities should conduct quarterly surveys and hold exchange sessions between students and university administrators to understand students' perceptions better and get more valuable information about students' unsatisfactory experiences. Besides, it is necessary to avoid solving problems carelessly and hastily since this can easily lead to negative emotions in students and undesirable outcomes. Previous studies have shown that a heartfelt apology can quickly help consumers get over negative emotions (Priluck, 2003; Msosa, 2019). Institutions should apologize and offer reasonable explanations as soon as they realize that a student has encountered failure occasioned. Moreover, universities should be positive and open-minded attitude while receiving feedback on service failures that cause unsatisfied experiences for students.

Secondly, higher education institutions should review and redesign their complaint procedures to enhance fairness. Institutions may conduct a systematic review to identify and eliminate inefficiencies, such as a comprehensive audit of procedures related to credit registration, dormitory, library, finance, and more. Effective procedures should be able to facilitate speedy or timely access to facilities, services, and resolution of service breakdowns. Furthermore,

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organizational procedures should be designed to indicate standards or response periods to encourage speedy resolution of student complaints. In addition, the management of higher educational institutions should conduct training sessions to enhance employees' knowledge and skill because they are the ones who directly contact and handle student complaints. Higher education managers should have a clear work assignment and responsibility policy for each department so that every member of staff knows their responsibility when a customer complaint is launched. This can help to address role conflicts and overlapping responsibilities when students are not assisted in time.

Thirdly, universities need to take action to encourage students to complain by developing complaint channels. For example, in addition to complaining directly, students can complain using anonymous comment boxes, online websites, university applications, or student support groups on social media. Besides, the institutions can also create Interactive Digital Signage to assist students when service failure occurs and direct them to the appropriate department to resolve the issue. Not only that, through a link to the university's software, Interactive Digital Signage can assist students in monitoring their complaint handling procedure. Higher education institutions also should publicize and simplify the handling service failures process so that students believe it is easier to complain.

Fourthly, employees in higher education institutions should be empowered to solve problems. This can help institutions reduce the time it takes to resolve students' complaints and also relieve pressure on higher management. Additionally, employee training is associated with empowerment, and this entails that employees who are knowledgeable and have the right skill sets will be able to make the right judgment when faced with a service failure incident.

VIII. LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Firstly, the sample size of this survey is limited. It is difficult to achieve high representativeness due to convenient samples, and this research only focuses on students studying the regular higher education program at the universities of economics. So, future studies can extend samples with a group of students studying high-quality programs, distance-learning, or conducting surveys at technology and engineering universities.

Secondly, there are many other factors influencing students' public complaint intention. Future research can pay more attention to the analysis of the customer's emotion and the severity of service failure that affect complaint intentions.

Thirdly, the research examines the service failure situations based on the recall method, so objectivity is not guaranteed.

Fourthly, the research focuses on the factors influencing students' public complaint intention. Thus, future studies can analyze and compare the factors that influence complainer and non-complainer behavior.

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